

STUDY OF TRADITIONAL ARCHITECTURE THROUGH INTEGRATED STUDIO:

A case of "Integrated Conservation & Regeneration Studio" (ICRS) in college of Architecture & Planning Qassim University

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ABSTRACT

This research paper emphasis on integrated approaches of learning method associated with architectural heritage conservation & regeneration, this integrated learning approach should be developing incipient knowledge of restoration and regeneration process in heritage study within the studio. It pursues to develop and venture of new knowledge for architecture heritage where the process of regeneration and restoration engages in both social concepts and realistic appearances. This is an innovative direction for Architectural Heritage conservation and its regeneration through an integrated learning approach named "*Integrated Studio Learning Module*". University based team of interdisciplinary area expert has implemented their group study over to the specific site in Qassim region. Though interdisciplinary learning module, the team has collect all related specific primary & secondary data for further study and implicated it's in to the "*interdisciplinary process model*" also each team discusses suitable specific area proposal & possibilities of incipient option for conservation and regeneration model in the given heritage site. The objectives to explore the prospective learning module for regeneration process as the essential element of architecture heritage education. To theorize, analyze, organize and generate new ideas through integrated studio. These all pedagogical approaches explore emerging learning trends in conservation and regeneration practice, as well as developing sustainable future for our built heritage.

KEY WORD: Studio education, Interdisciplinary Learning Module, Integrated Conservation & Regeneration Studio.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

An improvement of approaching architectural Heritage through a pedagogical approach named integrated studio learning (ISL). The College of architecture and planning Qassim University has implementing ISL in one of its core annual workshop, (Architectural Heritage Studies of the region) in collaboration with Authority for tourism and antique (SCATA). This approach has always been implemented in learning and teaching of architecture in studio (Master Program in Built Heritage). The main pedagogical approach was not discussed at the time of workshop planning; yet recent analysis on the course shows the existence of ISL principle in learning and teaching process of the course. The implementation of ISL pedagogical approach has proven to efficiently develop students' individuality in learning system, and enhance their proficiency in understanding Architectural Heritage study. Student groups are also found to gain conservation skill through this ISL, this workshop of Architectural Heritage requires students to initially select a local circle of given heritage area in the region and make condition survey through observatory studio. The purpose of the studio producing complete scientific

documentation of the buildings and their history, in the format of final studio workshop project, construction drawings, presentation drawings, architectural model, miniature artifact, digital multimedia documents, SWAT analysis, issues etc. [1] After buildings or area are identified, students are expected to have field work of measuring the buildings or cases survey of the heritage area and analysis them for more possibilities. On the bases of collecting data by students, the integrated studio approach implemented in this Heritage Studies workshop effectively. Students gain the conservation and regeneration knowledge completely other than traditional teaching, them via lectures in history of architecture classes. To be sure, more and integrated approaches of studio should be implemented by using ISL, to improve students' capabilities in making regeneration of built heritage of our society [2].

This paper is to investigate if ISL could be identified as the pedagogical approach applied to the workshop studio; to examine the essences of ISL within the workshop studio outline; and to study if ISL components have made learning more interesting as compared to the traditional teaching methods of lectures delivery. As a result, this study will frame the course to a theoretical approach that answer criticism that architectural heritage programme always lack of pedagogical framework [3]. As the current development of pedagogies actually challenge and address weaknesses in current practice of architectural education particularly in design studio [4], ISL may give sense of belonging to this course whilst developing students' independent learner culture. "From a provider of teaching to a producer of learning" [5], which would be relevant to tomorrow's architectural occupation.

2.0 PURPOSE AND OBJECTIVE OF STUDY

The purposes of this paper, to analysing of an integrated approach of cross disciplinary action associated to studio, for developing incipient idea in conservation and regeneration of build heritage. Identify factors that inhibit and facilitate the integration of interdisciplinary methods and provide a methodology for the institutionalization of integrated studio learning module (ISL). That learning module creating new methodology for conservation of heritage architecture in studio workshop.

The conception of the heritage study and implementation of it, even the unassuming architectural problem are almost completely collaborative with interdisciplinary activities, that demanding the proficiency of a variety of individuals working together to achieve a remarkable objective. Each of these expert group are highly trained in their individual areas, yet few are formally trained authorities in the skills of collaboration, including architects, individuals who are often put at the lead of conservation and regeneration which include people of diverse experiences, working styles and areas of proficiency.

1. *The question is raising – Can pedagogical approaches & techniques be instructed in the integrated conservation and regeneration studio ICRS, while during working process of that studio, without taking away from the inherent strengths of the traditional studio based architectural education?*
2. *Can integration of these studio & techniques be incipient new idea and trend in study of heritage conservation and regeneration through ISL?*

2.1 RESEARCH OUTCOME

The outcome of this research to explore the prospective of heritage study through studio learning module. As the essential element of architecture education to theorize, analyze, organize and generate new ideas through integrated interdisciplinary studio learning, the design process might be change and replace the tradition way of studio process and education system as well. These all education and practice based approaches explore incipient trends in Contemporary Architecture education & practice as well as developing new ideas for sustainable future—heritage built environments.

2.2 METHODOLOGY

Table 1: Methodology for research study (Source: Draft by author) 2015)

RESEARCH PROBLEM	METHODOLOGY TO BE ADOPTED
Understanding of approaching area for heritage conservation teaching.	Solve by related works reviews & discussion and condition survey of existing pedagogy.
Study of current scenario of heritage conservation and regeneration studios.	By related literature and condition surveys of conservation education course.
Investigate targeted group of participant opinion toward integration of ISL in collaborative studio.	Given heritage area of the region
Explore the involvement of interdisciplinary approaches, facilities and methodology for design and development in studio learning module.	Area exercise, data collection by area condition surveys.
Comparative analysis of results (similarities & differences) of problem based samples and presentation	Data analysis ,findings through SWAT and GD.

3.0 PEDAGOGY FOR ICRS STUDIO WORKSHOP

Integrated studio: Architectural Heritage Studies is a short credit skill based workshop course to be taken by level six architectural students. This workshop is a studio based collaborative, where students spend most of their time working collaboratively among group members to produce documentations of related heritage site and buildings surveyed. It introduces students to the general conservation and regeneration techniques, and exposes students to the practice of measuring and measuring heritage buildings, especially those which located in the native areas. The use of material technology and latest building measuring methods will also be incorporated in the workshop [6].

The objectives of this heritage studies workshop are: to encourage students' awareness on the importance and meanings of conserving architectural heritage; to develop students' skill in building measuring and building documentations, for the purpose of conservation and regeneration; to exposes students on multi-dimensional experience of managing their learning concerns: and expands student's capabilities in to understand rich cultural value of heritage area.

The course is conducted during end of 2 semesters. Being the shortest semester of seven (4 to 7) weeks only, it requires students to undergo rough and concentrated study period to complete the skill workshop. Workshop is at least 3 to 5 credit hours course, but as studio or lab based subject, it has minimum of six (12) contact hours per week in which students spend their time in working integrated design studio. Previous knowledge related to architectural documentation and presentation would be help full for pre-requisite; so that the prior knowledge gained form the course would enable students to work in individually as in collaborative environment.

3.2 LEARNING BY COLLABORATION (ISL) MODEL

The architectural discipline has the main effective factor of creating and developing a humane environment. Hence, architectural pedagogy should move towards the new trend of equipping students well to meet the demands of the fast developing construction industry, particularly in the enhancement of design-studio teaching [7]. In contemporary education system, the pedagogy contains a new requirement of professional practice, which increases the level of architectural design education through the integration of Interdisciplinarity i.e. associated with architecture. There are a number of international organizations such as the ACSA, NAAB and UNESCO which arise the issues and release charters for architectural education. However, [8] was the only organization which proposed the solution to this educational crisis by putting a standard objective for architectural education so as to mark a boundary for architecture education, as well as made some interpretations to find related pedagogy. The charter which particularly recommended the methodological aspect in architectural education is: *An ability of the technological application which respects the social, cultural and aesthetic needs, and aware of the appropriate use of structure and construction materials in architecture and their initial and maintenance cost.* [7][8], In facing the crisis of architectural integration with other subjects (Interdisciplinarity), UNESCO emphasizes studio in the architectural heritage teaching and divided it into three main parts: strategy, Proficiency /skill and knowledge; where knowledge should cover cultural and artistic studies, social studies, environmental studies, proposal studies, professional studies and technical studies.

3.3 The ICRS +ISL Model: The concept of Integration based on the stages of data collection and analysis process; however, processes finish their stage within or without any error repetition. The settings of the learning modules are constituted in several contextual elements. It consists of three major components in learning modules: essential learning module, investigative learning module and critique learning module (Figure 1). Each learning module must be attached with the respective interdisciplinary studio within the collective process stage. (For description see table-2) the focus and objective of to establish teaching & learning process through some contemporary conceptual approaches i.e. elemental, investigative and critical method of teaching process. The studio problem describes within the four main stages of development process, each stage of processes must be collaborating under the spatial action and supervision of required discipline e.g. allied and associated discipline of architecture. Sideways from focusing on the development of a common formal vocabulary and the skills needed to communicate technically and digitally, the pedagogical goals of these learning modules to developed various skills related to conservation and regeneration within the active collaboration and integration of required speciality.

Figure 1: Sequences for studio integration
(Source: Redraft by author) 2015)

Table 2: Integrated Studio Learning Module (Source: Draft by author 2015)

Sequences of interdisciplinary studios			Sequences of interdisciplinary learning			
Sr. No.	Studios	Description	Learning Style	Description	Interdisciplinarity Integration	Stage of Design process
1	(S-C)	Collective	(L-C)	Collaborative ,	Architecture core	Quantitative thinking
2	(S-A)	Analytical - Investigative	(L-A+L-C)	Integrated collaborative	Architecture+(Art, literature ,history& philosophy)	Analysis +Organize
3	(S-C')	Critique-Development	(L-A'+L-S)	Integrated collaborative	Architecture +Eng. Services +research	Synthesis+ Evaluation
4	(S-AP)	Aesthetical	(L-S+L-A')	Associated with creativity	Interior + Façade +Lighting +Landscape	Communication + Creativeness

4.0 IMPLEMENTATION OF MODEL FOR HERITAGE STUDY

Site work stage is the most challenging part of this studio: conducting heritage building analysis and researching for historical and constructional background of the identified heritage area. Both activities are done for the purpose of producing comprehensive documentation of the heritage buildings and their history, in the format of report, construction drawings, presentation drawings, architectural model, artifact, digital multimedia documents [9]. On the other hand there is socio cultural , demographic ,and conditional survey for identified the related issues .in conservation and regeneration process there are two phase commonly going parallel these are physical issues and development ,socio- cultural & economic issues and development .

Table 3: The ICRS working methodology and responsibility (Source: Redraft

INTEGRATED COLLABORATION (Groups of study)	RESPONSIBILITIES	INTERVENTIONAL RELATION	SUPPORT AND TOOLS
Information&(PS) Data	Primary & secondary data related to site i.e. drawing , condition pictures ,models etc.	Condition survey Measuring drawing Presentation drawing Physical existing model	Digital cameras, Video Camera, Voice Recorders, Computer Laboratory, Heritage Laboratory, Model Making Laboratory and Measuring devices

Investigative collaboration	Analysis and discussion	research on historical aspects of site ,Interviews experts on relevant subject ,Collecting archival material ,Documenting process of heritage curriculum	Books, Digital cameras, Video camera, Voice recorders Computers, and its peripherals Archival materials, Library facilities, Heritage Laboratory
Engineering & cross collaboration	Structural ,landscape, physical services solution	Structural and sites services analysis after analyzing of interventional area's issues	Mapping tools and other engineering equipment.
Digital fabrication and presentation	Comprehensive multimedia presentation and documentation	Producing multimedia, presentation Document all relevant materials into digital form, Building virtual model of building.	Computers and its Software: AutoCAD series or Max, Adobe Photoshop, etc. 3D image scanner Photography Laboratory, Heritage Laboratory

Almost, most of learning tools existed in ISL has been used in the pedagogic strategies of architectural heritage study studio workshop. It has developed student's skills; such as statement, critical perceptive, a rational and analytical approach to problems, reasoned decision making, and self-evaluation. These results of learning implementation could change the condition of architecture education in present society.

5.0 ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The sample survey and model exercise yielded many students. Side by side the corner of expertise and professional are also submitted their valuable suggestion and options. The lower than expected response rate has been attributed to the deadline of the project being the final day of studios. The students were asked to respond at that time.

To collect data for the comparison, a study of two sections of B. Arch class was compared. The classes consisted of core subject workshop at college of Architecture & Planning; the classes were composed of architecture studio as core subject.

Assessment of final report productivity shown in the graph is directly proportional to the yield of equal integration of required Interdisciplinarity in each phase of studio process. That the results of final design having major change in term of each phase of design process e.g. Organizing, sound technical knowledge with proposal, intelligent visualization, MEP and services and aesthetics services like interior, lighting, façade development and landscaping. In the other hand the team of professional in real time, they are followed both traditional and collaborative interdisciplinary method for project. that the result much higher for design productivity however the project or problem is real. The core key for finishing is coordination with expert and complete the project. Actually process of creativity and collaboration in each stage of studio need some required supplement of interdisciplinary knowledge.

Figure 2 & 3: (Left) Module effective ness graph (Source: Draft by author 2015), (Right) Module adoption percentage (Source: Draft by author 2015)

CONCLUSION

The majority of students are satisfied with their learning effort in heritage workshop. Nearby effectively gain the specified knowledge of the conservation and regeneration; students collectively agree that the conduct of studio workshop, effective for changing knowledge, skill for conservation and regeneration of related project. During the last year experience in conducting this studio workshop, the college of architecture & Planning has faced many challenges.

However, the objectives of the studio have been skillful as required after. The studio prepares not only students to collect knowledge on building heritage, but also develop various skills for them to easily explore the proficiency later. Thus, ISL tools have been successfully adapted to study architectural disciplines, both in normal design studio and Heritage studies course. Additional and supplementary architectural issues should be delivered via ISL and it's providing to students flexible adoptive learning process in studio.

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